

Supplementary Materials for
**A computational tool to infer enzyme activity using post-translational
modification profiling data**

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1. Supplementary Information

1.1 Motif-assisted prediction strategy boosts the scope of enzyme-substrate relationships

The efficacy of kinase activity analysis is fundamentally linked to the completeness of kinase-substrate relationships. The current public databases primarily harbor known kinase-substrate relations, imposing limitations on the depth and scope of the analyses. To address this limitation, JUMPsem employs a motif-assisted prediction strategy, leveraging known motif sequences to identify new kinase-substrate relationships not available in the curated databases (Supplementary Figure S4). For each kinase, we first create a table containing all motif sequences from the PSP database. The program then utilizes the MEME tool to build consensus motifs for each kinase. These consensus motifs are processed by the MAST tool to identify any substrate sequences in the measured phosphoproteomics data. Newly identified kinase-substrate relationships are subsequently integrated to the kinase-substrate adjacency matrix.

1.2 Use case

1.2.1. Background

JUMPsem is a computational tool designed to infer enzyme activity from mass spectrometry-based post-translational modification data (e.g., phosphoproteome) using structural equation modeling (SEM). The program uses an enzyme-substrate relationship table from the public database (e.g., PhosphoSitePlus) as its primary input. The outputs of JUMPsem include activity and affinity tables. JUMPsem is an effective tool for enzyme activity inference, available as an open-source R package.

1.2.2 Analysis procedure

Installation: To install and load JUMPsem, use one of the following methods:

Local installation:

```
install.packages("JUMPsem_1.0.tar.gz", repos = NULL, type = "source")  
library(JUMPsem)
```

or

Github installation:

```
if (!requireNamespace("BiocManager", quietly=TRUE))
```

```
install.packages("BiocManager")
remotes::install_github("Wanglab-UTHSC/JUMPsem")
```

After installation, you can load the JUMPsem environment with the command below:

```
library(JUMPsem)
```

1.2.3. Preparing source data

1.2.3.1 Post-translational modification (PTM) proteomics data

To demonstrate the usage of JUMPsem, we take phosphoproteomics data as an example to infer kinase activity. If inferring other enzyme activity, PTM data can be organized similarly.

The input phosphoproteomics table should be formatted as follows:

Column 1: Substrate_ACC

- Lists the UniProt Accession number for each substrate.
- Missing values are not allowed. Use "NA" if the UniProt Accession is unknown.

Column 2: Substrate_GN

- Provides the gene symbol for each substrate.
- Use "NA" if the gene symbol is unavailable.

Column 3: Sites

- Lists modification site(s) in each substrate. Multiple sites within a single peptide should be delimited by commas (e.g., S12,Y15) and can optionally end with a comma.
- The site(s) in this column are highly recommended for phosphorylation data and accepts "NA" if unknown.

Column 4: Peptide

- Contains the modification site peptide for each substrate.
- Missing values are not allowed; if unknown, use "NA".

Column 5 and Beyond: Sample Quantifications

- Each column beyond Column 4 represents a sample with post-translational modification peptide quantifications. The number of columns can vary based on the number of samples in the analysis.

An example of the phosphoproteomics table:

Substrate_ACC	Substrate_GN	sites	Peptide	Sample_1	Sample_2	Sample_3	Sample_4	Sample_5	Sample_6	Sample_7	Sample_8	Sample_9	Sample_10
QBR2R3	Aagab	S311	AFWMAIGGDRDEIEGLSSDDEH	32144.9006	32942.21032	32971.57568	39104.32722	35927.50359	34894.54057	31757.42518	33978.87695	34797.70395	27780.66424
Q3UHU0	Aak1	S13	EQGSSGLGSGSSGGGSSGLGSGYIGR	10891.54438	10460.80881	13506.11116	8090.201223	2449.401632	8241.030217	7349.309092	8407.697301	8222.818829	8241.365152
Q3UHU0	Aak1	S18	EQGSSGLGSGSSGGGSSGLGSGYIGR	413309.9551	408662.3269	409886.3132	275592.558	265776.3178	298367.0148	306761.8362	310807.0964	320115.5378	286912.8071
Q3UHU0	Aak1	S20	EQGSSGLGSGSSGGGSSGLGSGYIGR	78218.40427	82862.8041	78529.43463	62278.76796	62592.40422	65527.58217	72085.82367	69577.19618	70681.7144	68785.97099
Q3THG9	Aarsd1	S409	GAQADHFTESPLSPGSGVQVR	11586.33566	10519.39649	11560.64696	12776.15846	12896.57441	12845.78788	12226.57959	12501.83839	11332.50228	11681.6012
Q3THG9	Aarsd1	S88	GAQADHFTESPLSPGSGVQVR	132607.4277	147176.7491	129679.6174	147829.0516	120542.0133	124033.4385	102881.203	125130.987	112030.6808	102234.2877
Q9IKX4	Aatf	S283	HIVNGAKPNTSESEISDEDELVGEK	98355.90649	93580.47082	86204.32117	187771.725	145005.4042	162362.4525	157510.8615	134988.9681	143487.475	164201.0137
Q9IKX4	Aatf	S287	HIVNGAKPNTSESEISDEDELVGEK	190902.2832	193764.4932	172575.2112	374532.9241	333329.7718	375312.6491	382934.7032	308327.6074	302091.1077	379514.0486
Q9IKX4	Aatf	S288	HIVNGAKPNTSESEISDEDELVGEK	190902.2832	193764.4932	172575.2112	374532.9241	333329.7718	375312.6491	382934.7032	308327.6074	302091.1077	379514.0486
Q8OYE4	Aatk	S1032	SLRPGGSTGLGSGSAAPAAATAASAEHTAASSFLLER	49604.79277	52540.921	51356.97427	35390.82027	39652.08073	48847.03605	35137.84959	52287.32944	31911.27666	37146.40005
Q8OYE4	Aatk	S1035	SLRPGGSTGLGSGSAAPAAATAASAEHTAASSFLLER	73178.45179	79939.88403	80563.1095	60921.10506	63079.4906	86869.04235	54693.30264	84158.59855	48270.03034	56435.863

1.2.3.2 Whole proteome data

Normalization with Whole Proteome Data

Normalization is performed by dividing the phosphoproteomics quantification values by their corresponding whole proteome quantification values for each sample. This step adjusts for protein abundance and enhances the accuracy of kinase activity inference. If normalization is required, PTM data can be normalized using whole proteome quantification data. Organize the whole proteome table as follows:

Column 1: Substrate_ACC

- Lists the UniProt Accession number of each substrate. Missing values are not allowed.

Column 2: Substrate_GN

- Provides the gene symbol for each substrate, with "NA" used for substrates without gene symbols.

Column 3 and Beyond: Sample Whole Proteome Quantifications

- Each additional column represents whole proteome quantification data for each sample. These columns should match the sample names in the phosphoproteomics table exactly. While the order does not need to be the same, matching order is recommended for simplicity.

An example of the whole proteome table:

Substrate_ACC	Substrate_GN	Sample_1	Sample_2	Sample_3	Sample_4	Sample_5	Sample_6	Sample_7	Sample_8	Sample_9	Sample_10
Q3UHJ0	Aak1	4489630.098	4346569.441	4441379.082	2796326.661	2712238.64	2717338.552	3024981.068	2352770.342	2371083.335	2566117.146
Q99K67	Aass	267032.8221	226106.6223	234903.8123	154909.1017	159680.3098	149103.1649	153406.0578	140683.2629	130885.6365	134470.2838
Q80YE4	Aatk	171653.3031	168656.1032	175141.9542	141703.5628	143767.8074	149729.5882	141733.0791	104555.7107	107366.5608	119103.3164
P61922	Abat	27797166.89	28633714.94	25162152.75	18166091.6	20668252.14	17246196.83	18888069.26	12676995.01	14481988.81	17796735.28
Q8K448	Abca5	691956.1391	675459.429	669629.8162	508182.837	508242.7349	429991.1483	414846.3907	368278.0902	387581.2552	398352.5248
Q9JI39	Abcb10	247595.1462	244238.5982	280077.6598	231515.4668	234292.6609	228570.3781	231884.9504	148489.4004	157044.9124	185582.111
Q9CXJ4	Abcb8	420116.3135	431109.8723	433010.264	300376.8088	320865.3491	274326.3141	296253.7261	272415.7108	257222.7551	298952.4591
Q9JJ59	Abcb9	423106.947	429731.2655	399918.4063	323039.3708	316000.2864	305283.2458	251658.3021	181767.166	188348.3378	254268.2435
B2RUS7	Abcc8	469902.6743	451827.6613	442857.3337	246063.8751	243558.221	235671.7263	256833.837	177598.4002	186363.8868	210789.8997
Q91WA9	Abcg4	96764.19552	98365.58732	95687.3203	70797.06455	74087.0746	67255.94161	68965.62772	56510.00892	56838.61997	68825.82692

1.2.3. JUMPsem results

JUMPsem helps to infer enzyme activities and organize them into four result tables including Activity_Raw.txt, Activity_Zscore.txt, Activity_MeanCenter.txt and Affinity.txt.

Column 1: ENZYME

- Lists the enzyme names.

Column 2 and Beyond: Sample Activity Inference

- Each column beyond Column 1 represents a sample with inferred activity. The number of columns is based on the number of samples in the input data.

An example of the Activity_* table:

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K
1	ENZYME	Cortex_1	Cortex_2	Cortex_3	PDGFRA_4	PDGFRA_5	PDGFRA_6	PDGFRA_7	NTRK_8	NTRK_9	NTRK_10
2	PRKCD	-0.936470748	-0.809415329	-0.823214747	0.179225346	-0.179098105	-0.229804849	-0.180376535	1.584343676	1.95393835	-0.559127058
3	PIM2	0.080008814	-0.486391972	-0.621586819	2.290231401	0.630282689	0.443807474	-0.774919195	0.068162307	-0.267835395	-1.361759302
4	CAMK2A	0.119867171	0.230664818	0.30150054	-0.022221063	0.245815322	-0.01542427	-1.728868115	1.344656817	1.153046344	-1.629037564
5	CSNK2A1	-1.443142132	-1.228516294	-1.368500565	0.302624844	0.211239537	0.509004745	0.043553858	1.086939761	1.240610098	0.646186148
6	MAPK8	-0.894871347	-0.173395445	-1.040262549	1.979883802	0.277055776	0.688765386	-0.708735374	-0.465231931	-0.790883757	1.127675438
7	EGFR	-0.116126406	0.188715436	0.053619796	-1.179025086	-0.837805877	-0.790606688	-0.785668672	1.976626237	0.199165152	1.291106107
8	FYN	-1.276544337	-0.917254442	-1.132106391	1.06999554	0.558475929	-0.049672701	-0.605414072	1.127459404	1.449215228	-0.224154159
9	PRKAA1	-1.257530039	-0.687878669	-1.453423894	0.694476632	0.08581265	0.696201891	-0.455200873	1.655358679	-0.209191742	0.931375364
10	PRKAA2	-1.342213052	-1.008832573	-1.573542214	0.651297128	0.008065226	0.70553986	0.102836916	1.364373986	0.150128753	0.942345969

Note: Activity results are generated into raw values, z-score transformed and normalized by mean centered.

Column 1: ENZYME_GN

- ENZYME_GN column contains the enzyme name.

Column 2: SUB_ACC_ID

- SUB_ACC_ID column contains the UniProt Accession number of each substrate.

Column 3: SUBSTRATE_GN

- SUBSTRATE_GN column contains the gene symbol for each substrate, with "NA" used for substrates without gene symbols.

Column 4: SUB_sites

- SUB_sites are modification site(s) in each substrate.
- This column is based on phosphorylation resource data and reports "NA" if in resource data.

Column 5: AFFINITY

- This column represents the relationship between enzyme and relative substrate.

Column 6: z

- This column represents z-value. It indicates how many standard deviations an observed value is from the mean of a distribution.

Column 7: Pvalue

- This column provides the probability of observing a z-score.

An example of the Affinity table:

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
1	ENZYME_GN	SUB_ACC_ID	SUBSTRATE_GN	SUB_sites	AFFINITY	z	Pvalue
2	PRKCD	P14602	Hspb1	S86	1	NA	NA
3	PRKCD	P28867	Prkcd	S643	7.912133985	0.30200861	0.762645499
4	PRKCD	Q62318	Trim28	S473	-1.049149188	-1.043007831	0.296944666
5	CAMK2A	P35436	Grin2a	S1459	1	NA	NA
6	CAMK2A	P54227	Stmn1	S16	0.357692504	1.602889245	0.108959109
7	CAMK2A	O88935	Syn1	S605	1.243213579	1.872142525	0.061186888
8	CAMK2A	F6SEU4	Syngap1	S780	0.524020621	1.230745062	0.218418229
9	CAMK2A	P63044	Vamp2	S61	1.399365268	2.003426214	0.04513156
10	CAMK2A	P20152	Vim	S83	-1.400842351	-1.66685813	0.095542618

1.3. Implication for the community

JUMPsem is a computational tool used to infer protein enzyme activity from post-translational modification (PTM) profiling data. The modular and scalable architecture of

the JUMPsem package, combined with an accessible web application interface, enhances its utility for enzyme activity inference. Compared to similar existing software, we uniquely demonstrate the versatility of JUMPsem by applying it to three different proteomic datasets - the phosphoproteome, the ubiquitin proteome, and the acetyl proteome - enabling precise quantification of enzyme activity and substrate interactions. The capacity of JUMPsem to estimate enzyme activity and elucidate cellular signaling pathways underscores its potential as an indispensable resource in proteomics research.

2. Supplementary Figures

Figure S1. Detailed workflow of the JUMPsem implementation.

Figure S2. Normalization procedure used in JUMPsem.

Figure S3. Workflow of the data processing procedure in JUMPsem.

Figure S4. The workflow diagram details of the kinase motif-assisted prediction process.

Figure S5. Performance evaluation of JUMPsem versus IKAP using benchmark datasets.

3. Supplementary Tables

Supplementary Table 1a. KEGG enrichment analysis of altered kinases between NTRK1 and control from JUMPsem results.

Supplementary Table 1b. KEGG enrichment analysis of altered kinases between PDGFRA and control from JUMPsem results.

Supplementary Table 1c. KEGG enrichment analysis of altered kinases between PDGFRA and control from IKAP results.

Supplementary Table 1d. KEGG enrichment analysis of altered kinases between NTRK1 and control from IKAP results.

Supplementary Table 2. JUMPsem program detected altered kinases with differential activities between P31/Fuj (Fuj) and Kasumi-1 (Kasm) cells in human data with motif assisted.

Supplementary Table 3a. Enrichment analysis from kinases with differential activities calculated by IKAP between P31/Fuj (Fuj) and Kasumi-1 (Kasm) cell lines.

Supplementary Table 3b. Enrichment analysis from kinases with differential activities calculated by JUMPsem with motifs between P31/Fuj (Fuj) and Kasumi-1 (Kasm) cell lines.

Supplementary Table 4. Enzyme ligase activity analysis by JUMPsem.

Supplementary Table 5. Benchmark datasets used for performance comparison.

Supplementary Figures

Figure S1. Detailed workflow of the JUMPsem implementation.

Figure S2. Normalization procedure used in JUMPsem. The process begins with two raw input matrices: phosphoproteomic matrix and its corresponding whole proteome matrix if available. Both matrices undergo a \log_2 transformation, followed by a mean scaling (relative transformation). Subsequently, the normalized phosphoproteomic matrix is obtained by subtracting the protein level from the corresponding phosphopeptide.

Figure S3. Workflow of the data processing procedure in JUMPsem. The process begins with the normalized phosphoproteomic matrix (Figure S3), which is matched to corresponding kinases based on known associations in the PTM database. Separate matrices are then generated for each kinase, which serve as input for JUMPsem. Various parameters (e.g., cor.off, kmo.off, mdsite, enzyList) are used within JUMPsem to control model fitting and other data processing steps.

Figure S4. The workflow diagram details of the kinase motif-assisted prediction process. The process starts from motif table compilation from the PSP database to the establishment of new kinase-substrate relationships via MEME and MAST tools, culminating in an expanded kinase-substrate adjacency matrix.

Figure S5. Performance evaluation of JUMPsem versus IKAP using benchmark datasets. (a) Schematic diagram showing the evaluation method. Phosphorylation input tables from each condition were used to establish substrate-kinase relationships. Kinase activity was inferred for each kinase, and the average activity across replicates was calculated. (b) Kinases were ranked based on their average activity, and the rank of the target kinase was recorded. Precision was calculated using the rank of the target kinase, where a true positive was defined as the target kinase having a rank smaller than a pre-defined threshold. (c) Precision-recall curves comparing the performance of JUMPsem (red) and IKAP (blue) in identifying target kinases across benchmark datasets. JUMPsem demonstrates higher precision across a range of target kinase ranks.